

Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation and Registration

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

N/A

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are increasingly popular in modern dental practice, particularly for treatment planning or comprehensive prognosis evaluation. With the advancement of oral digitalization and three-dimensional scanning technology, cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and intraoral scanning (IOS) have been widely applied in clinical dental treatment. In digital orthodontic treatment, the high-precision reconstruction of teeth is crucial. While traditional intraoral scanning (IOS) models offer high resolution, relying solely on IOS data for treatment carries the risk of insufficient root information. Conversely, CBCT provides comprehensive information on both crowns and roots, but its scanning resolution is lower, and it contains more redundant information. Therefore, combining the two can better utilize their complementary strengths, enhancing the precision and efficiency of dental treatment. Furthermore, automated and precise evaluation of root pulp canals in CBCT images holds significant importance, as it can substantially enhance the precision and efficiency of root pulp canals treatment. Precise segmentation of the root pulp canal allows for a clearer visualization of its morphology, branches, and curvatures, facilitating the development of more refined filling strategies. However, the annotation of tooth root pulp canal regions in CBCT images is inherently labor-intensive, requiring a substantial investment of time and human resources. Furthermore, CBCT and IOS image registration tasks also rely on expert manual delineation of corresponding points or regions in both datasets as registration references, presenting similar challenges in terms of time and manpower costs.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Intraoral scan, CBCT, Registration, Segmentation, Semi-supervised

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

1. Existing challenges within the field predominantly focus on segmenting the coronal and root portion of teeth, overlooking the crucial aspect of precise pulp canal evaluation. This challenge introduces a novel, fully annotated CBCT semi-supervised segmentation dataset with annotation of whole teeth part and pulp canal. Beyond teeth segmentation, our dataset uniquely provides voxel-level annotations for the root canal region, representing the first publicly available resource of this nature within the research community.

2. This challenge presents the largest publicly available semi-supervised dataset for CBCT and IOS image registration, comprising a combination of partially annotated paired images alongside a substantial volume of unlabeled data. This extensive resource facilitates the development and evaluation of novel semi-supervised registration algorithms.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

N/A

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

DentalGroup Workshop

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

In the previously held MICCAI Semi-TeethSeg 2024 challenge, over 180 teams successfully registered. Based on this, we estimate that at least 100 teams will participate in the challenge scheduled for 2025.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed two co-authorships

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Assuming that MICCAI will take place in person, we need support for basic presentation equipment (e.g. projectors, computers, monitors, loud speakers, microphones), for solution presentations from the top-ranked teams.

TASK 1: Semi-supervised CBCT-IOS registration

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are increasingly popular in modern dental practice, particularly for treatment planning or comprehensive prognosis evaluation. With the advancement of oral digitalization and three-dimensional scanning technology, cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and intraoral scanning (IOS) have been widely applied in clinical dental treatment. In digital orthodontic treatment, the high-precision reconstruction of teeth is crucial. While traditional intraoral scanning (IOS) models offer high resolution, relying solely on IOS data for treatment carries the risk of insufficient root information. Conversely, CBCT provides comprehensive information on both crowns and roots, but its scanning resolution is lower, and it contains more redundant information. Therefore, combining the two can better utilize their complementary strengths, enhancing the precision and efficiency of dental treatment. Furthermore, automated and precise evaluation of root pulp canals in CBCT images holds significant importance, as it can substantially enhance the precision and efficiency of root pulp canals treatment. Precise segmentation of the root pulp canal allows for a clearer visualization of its morphology, branches, and curvatures, facilitating the development of more refined filling strategies. However, the annotation of tooth root pulp canal regions in CBCT images is inherently labor-intensive, requiring a substantial investment of time and human resources. Furthermore, CBCT and IOS image registration tasks also rely on expert manual delineation of corresponding points or regions in both datasets as registration references, presenting similar challenges in terms of time and manpower costs.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.

Dahong Qian, School of Biomedical Engineering, Shanghai JiaoTong University, China.

Shuai Wang, School of Cyberspace Security, Hangzhou Dianzi University, China.

Jun Liu, School of Electronics and Information Engineering, Hangzhou Dianzi University, China.

Yifan Zhang, Hangzhou Geriatric Stomatology Hospital, Hangzhou Dental Hospital Group, Division of Advanced Prosthetic Dentistry, Tohoku University Graduate School of Dentistry, State Key Laboratory of Oral Diseases, National Clinical Research Center for Oral Diseases, West China Hospital of Stomatology, Sichuan University, China.

Lan Feng, Sir Run Run Shaw Hospital, Zhejiang University, China.

Yufeng Xie Department of Periodontology Shanghai Stomatological Hospital & School of Stomatology, Fudan University, China.

Hongbo Yu, Department of Oral and Craniomaxillofacial Surgery, Shanghai Ninth People's Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine, China.

Peter Wu, General Manager's Office, Guilin Kevin Peter Technology Co., Ltd, China.

Yang Yang, Department of Digital Technology, Guilin Kevin Peter Technology Co., Ltd, China.

Hongyuan Zhang, School of Biomedical Engineering, Shenzhen University, China.

Chengyu Wu, Department of Mechanical, Electrical and Information Engineering, Shandong University, China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.

Email: wangyaqi@cuz.edu.cn.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench platform

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.codabench.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide a prize (cash and certificate) for the top three teams. The exact money of cash prize is not known yet. Sponsors for the awards are currently being investigated. The details of this will be announced on our challenge homepage at a later date.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the challenge. But only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed two co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when adhering to the data usage rules, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions will be made via Docker container. The participating teams should upload their algorithm to the online submission system.

We will look for sponsors for computing resources. If it is not available, we will use our local hardware. It has two 8-Cores CPUs, one NVIDIA 2080Ti GPU, and 64G RAM. Only one GPU is allowed to use during inference.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their algorithm on validation set three times before a pre-defined deadline and only once on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Announcement of challenge's opening: March 15th, 2025
 - Open for registration and Training data release: March 20th, 2025
 - Deadline for validation submission: June 15th, 2025
 - Deadline for testing submission: July 15th, 2025
 - Invitation speakers: No later than September 1st, 2025
 - Announce final results: October 6th/10th, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The usage of dataset adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the data were carefully reviewed and approved by the Medical Ethics Committees of Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital (Approval ID: 20220484) and Lishui College School of Medicine (Approval ID: 2022YR014)

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND --

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 10 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the teeth segmentation challenge.

Only organizing members of the challenge has access to the test case labels during and after the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Decision support, Diagnosis, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Registration

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is patients who are requiring orthodontic treatment.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes individuals with dental treatment. 3D Cone Beam Computed Tomography scan are collected from patients dentition requiring orthodontic, and endodontic prosthetic treatment. The Intraoral Scan are collected from patients who were suffer from the oral disease, such as caries, periodontal disease, malocclusion, tooth loss, tooth wear, etc.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Cone beam computed tomography, Intraoral Scan

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional context information will be given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The dataset comprises 660 patients with ages ranging from 5 to 86 years (mean \pm standard deviation: 38.60 ± 16.56 years), ensuring a broad demographic representation. This diverse age range enhances the dataset's applicability across a wide spectrum of patient populations. The median age for male patients is 41 years (interquartile range [IQR]: 27–56), while for female patients, it is 30 years (IQR: 23–47). The dataset demonstrates a balanced sex distribution (51.06% male, 48.94% female), reducing the potential for sex-related biases in AI model development and evaluation.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Data is acquired for the intraoral cavity. For a given patient, CBCT scans will be acquired covering full/part of the upper and lower jaws with teeth, IOS scans will be acquired covering full mouth of teeth and gingiva

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker container that can perform accurate registration between CBCT and IOS.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All the 3D CBCT scans were acquired with a OP300, manufactured by Instrumentarium Orthopantomograph®. CBCT slices were acquired in the DICOM format at the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China Hospital. All CBCT slices were scanned before dental operations, with a resolution of 266×266 pixels in the axial view. The in-plane resolution is about $0.25 \times 0.25\text{mm}^2$ and the slice thickness range from 0.25 mm to 0.3 mm.

The IOS scans were acquired with equipment manufactured by ITERO®, SHINING 3D ®and 3SHAPE®. The

patients in this experiment were from patients who received informed consent from West China Stomatology Hospital of Sichuan University, Hangzhou Children's Stomatology Hospital, and Hangzhou Qiantang Dental Hospital.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

In general, no particular protocol is defined for the 3D IOS scans and 3D CBCT scans

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The patients in this experiment were from patients who received informed consent from West China Stomatology Hospital of Sichuan University, Hangzhou Children's Stomatology Hospital, and Hangzhou Qiantang Dental Hospital. Part of the dataset are from our previous challenge: MICCAI Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation Challenge (<https://sts-challenge.github.io/miccai2024/index.html>)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired by orthodontists with more than five years of professional experience. Scans were annotated by fifteen dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually marked all teeth landmarks.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training cases represent paired CBCT and IOS scans associated with/without the landmark annotation. Test cases represent paired CBCT and IOS scans with landmark annotation. Several disease types were included in this dataset such as pulpitis caries, impacted tooth and apical periodontitis to ensure the generalizability of the proposed algorithm to various clinical scenarios.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set: 30 paired CBCT-IOS, 220 paired CBCT-IOS

Validation set: 20 paired CBCT-IOS

Test set: 30 paired CBCT-IOS

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge is designed for benchmarking semi-supervised learning methods. Thus, only a small set of cases of paired CBCT and IOS are labeled and a large number of unlabeled cases can be used for training.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data are from a large real-life scenarios, thus the class distribution is representative of the real-world distribution.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

There is no unseen teeth types in the testing set. All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The landmark were annotated by 15 dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually annotated. Three senior experts with at least ten years of experience were invited to evaluate the annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For 3D CBCT scans, professional annotation software ITKSNAP (<http://www.itksnap.org/pmwiki/pmwiki.php>) was in charge of performing the annotations for dentists. For IOS scans, professional annotation software 3d Slicer (<https://www.slicer.org/>) was utilized for landmark annotation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Twelve junior dentists first annotate the landmark. Next, the senior dentists experts assessed the annotation quality, and marked a quality level (excellent, good, fail and poor) on each tooth annotation. "Excellent" annotations were deemed satisfactory and retained without further adjustments. "Good" annotations were fine-tuning according to the experts' feedback. "Fair" and "Poor" annotations and their feedback were put back into the unlabelled data pool and were marked again. To ensure the consistency of the annotation, we perform the following operation: 1. randomly selected 30% cases were annotated by all annotators; 2. Calculated ICC coefficients; 3. Assessed multi-annotator agreement using Fleiss' Kappa; Re-annotate the cases with low ICC and Fleiss' Kappa.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No preprocessing steps are required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Error is unavoidable in medical image registration. Landmarks were annotated by 15 dentists including twelve junior dentists and three senior dentists. Since much of the annotation process is manual, there may be boundary inaccuracies in the root region. Fortunately, the quality control approach will largely reduce this source of error. Moreover, We will have a github repository to collect feedbacks from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset. This strategy was also used in MICCAI KiTS and FLARE Challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The registration results are evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Normalized Cross-Correlation (NCC) and Normalized Mutual Information (NMI). All metrics will be used to compute the ranking. We will release the code on how to calculate the eight performance metrics with the python3 version.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The RMSE is an intuitive, computationally efficient, and easy way to access the registration result, this metric is computed using the predicted landmarks and the annotated landmarks. NCC is robust to variations in brightness and contrast, making it a popular choice for images with different modalities. NMI models the probabilistic relation between the voxel intensities of the images, which making it the primary similarity metric used in multi-modal image registration.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking scheme includes the following three steps:

Step 1. Compute the four metrics for each testing case between the ground truth and the results from the participants.

Step 2. Take the mean of these metrics over the test cases, and rank separately among the teams.

Step 3. A final overall rank is given by taking the average of these ranks. In the case of equal average rankings for two teams, they are considered tied.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in MICCAI BraTS Challenge.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set. Besides the statistical values such as mean, standard deviation of the metrics, we use the p-value in Wilcoxon test to assess whether the top performing/ranking algorithms are significantly better than the rest of algorithms. To ensure statistical reliability of rankings, we plan to implement the statistical significance testing via bootstrap resamples for the teams, to avoid the uncertainty occurred in the test phase.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon test is chosen because it is non-parametric and allows us to perform the analysis with minimal hypotheses, and the Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: Semi-supervised Root Pulp Canals Segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Computer-aided diagnosis tools are increasingly popular in modern dental practice, particularly for treatment planning or comprehensive prognosis evaluation. With the advancement of oral digitalization and three-dimensional scanning technology, cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and intraoral scanning (IOS) have been widely applied in clinical dental treatment. In digital orthodontic treatment, the high-precision reconstruction of teeth is crucial. While traditional intraoral scanning (IOS) models offer high resolution, relying solely on IOS data for treatment carries the risk of insufficient root information. Conversely, CBCT provides comprehensive information on both crowns and roots, but its scanning resolution is lower, and it contains more redundant information. Therefore, combining the two can better utilize their complementary strengths, enhancing the precision and efficiency of dental treatment. Furthermore, automated and precise evaluation of root pulp canals in CBCT images holds significant importance, as it can substantially enhance the precision and efficiency of root pulp canals treatment. Precise segmentation of the root pulp canal allows for a clearer visualization of its morphology, branches, and curvatures, facilitating the development of more refined filling strategies. However, the annotation of tooth root pulp canal regions in CBCT images is inherently labor-intensive, requiring a substantial investment of time and human resources. Furthermore, CBCT and IOS image registration tasks also rely on expert manual delineation of corresponding points or regions in both datasets as registration references, presenting similar challenges in terms of time and manpower costs.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.

Dahong Qian, School of Biomedical Engineering, Shanghai JiaoTong University, China.

Shuai Wang, School of Cyberspace Security, Hangzhou Dianzi University, China.

Jun Liu, School of Electronics and Information Engineering, Hangzhou Dianzi University, China.

Yifan Zhang, Hangzhou Geriatric Stomatology Hospital, Hangzhou Dental Hospital Group, Division of Advanced Prosthetic Dentistry, Tohoku University Graduate School of Dentistry, State Key Laboratory of Oral Diseases, National Clinical Research Center for Oral Diseases, West China Hospital of Stomatology, Sichuan University, China.

Lan Feng, Sir Run Run Shaw Hospital, Zhejiang University, China.

Yufeng Xie Department of Periodontology Shanghai Stomatological Hospital & School of Stomatology, Fudan University, China.

Hongbo Yu, Department of Oral and Craniomaxillofacial Surgery, Shanghai Ninth People's Hospital, Shanghai Jiao Tong University School of Medicine, China.

Peter Wu, General Manager's Office, Guilin Kevin Peter Technology Co., Ltd, China.

Yang Yang, Department of Digital Technology, Guilin Kevin Peter Technology Co., Ltd, China.

Hongyuan Zhang, School of Biomedical Engineering, Shenzhen University, China.

Chengyu Wu, Department of Mechanical, Electrical and Information Engineering, Shandong University, China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Yaqi Wang, College of Media Engineering, Communication University of Zhejiang, China.

Email: wangyaqi@cuz.edu.cn.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

CodaBench platform

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.codabench.org/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

We will provide a prize (cash and certificate) for the top three teams. The exact money of cash prize is not known yet. Sponsors for the awards are currently being investigated. The details of this will be announced on our challenge homepage at a later date.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All results will be announced publicly through a public leaderboard and each participating team will receive the model validation results after the challenge. But only the team that submits the method description paper will be eligible for the final ranking.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

An overview paper will be written with the organizing team's members. Each participating team who presented their method at the challenge session is allowed two co-authorships. The participating teams are encouraged to publish their results separately elsewhere when adhering to the data usage rules, and (if so) no embargo will be applied.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Submissions will be made via Docker container. The participating teams should upload their algorithm to the online submission system.

We will look for sponsors for computing resources. If it is not available, we will use our local hardware. It has two 8-Cores CPUs, one NVIDIA 2080Ti GPU, and 64G RAM. Only one GPU is allowed to use during inference.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to validate their algorithm on validation set three times before a pre-defined deadline and only once on the testing set.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
 - the registration date/period
 - the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
 - the submission date(s)
 - associated workshop days (if any)
 - the release date(s) of the results
- Announcement of challenge's opening: March 15th, 2025
 - Open for registration and Training data release: March 20th, 2025
 - Deadline for validation submission: June 15th, 2025
 - Deadline for testing submission: July 15th, 2025
 - Invitation speakers: No later than September 1st, 2025
 - Announce final results: October 6th/10th, 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The usage of dataset adhered to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and the data were carefully reviewed and approved by the Medical Ethics Committees of Sichuan Provincial People's Hospital (Approval ID: 20220484) and Lishui College School of Medicine (Approval ID: 2022YR014)

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND --

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Evaluation code will be made available with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Top 10 teams should make their code publicly available. The remaining teams are encouraged to make their code publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no explicit sponsoring/funding of the challenge, but we aim to contact technology companies with an interest in the teeth segmentation challenge.

Only organizing members of the challenge has access to the test case labels during and after the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE**Field(s) of application**

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD, Decision support, Diagnosis, Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort is patients who are requiring endodontic prosthetic and pulpitis treatment.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes individuals with dental treatment. 3D Cone Beam Computed Tomography scan are collected from patients dentition requiring orthodontic, and endodontic prosthetic treatment.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Cone beam computed tomography

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

No additional context information will be given.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

The dataset comprises 660 patients with ages ranging from 5 to 86 years (mean \pm standard deviation: 38.60 \pm 16.56 years), ensuring a broad demographic representation. This diverse age range enhances the dataset's applicability across a wide spectrum of patient populations. . The median age for male patients is 41 years

(interquartile range [IQR]: 27–56), while for female patients, it is 30 years (IQR: 23–47). The dataset demonstrates a balanced sex distribution (51.06% male, 48.94% female), reducing the potential for sex-related biases in AI model development and evaluation.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Data is acquired for the intraoral cavity. For a given patient, CBCT scans will be acquired covering full/part of the upper and lower jaws with teeth,

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Participants have to submit a Docker container that can segment root pulp canal accurately.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

All the 3D CBCT scans were acquired with a OP300, manufactured by Instrumentarium Orthopantomograph®. CBCT slices were acquired in the DICOM format at the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China Hospital. All CBCT slices were scanned before dental operations, with a resolution of 266×266 pixels in the axial view. The in-plane resolution is about 0.25×0.25 mm² and the slice thickness range from 0.25 mm to 0.3 mm.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

In general, no particular protocol is defined for the 3D IOS scans and 3D CBCT scans

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The patients in this experiment were from patients who received informed consent from West China Stomatology Hospital of Sichuan University, Hangzhou Children's Stomatology Hospital, and Hangzhou Qiantang Dental Hospital. Part of the dataset are from our previous challenge: MICCAI Semi-supervised Teeth Segmentation Challenge (<https://sts-challenge.github.io/miccai2024/index.html>)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired by orthodontists with more than five years of professional experience. Scans were annotated by fifteen dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually marked all root pulp canal.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Training cases represent a single CBCT scan associated with/without corresponding root pulp canal annotation. Test cases represent a single CBCT scan associated with corresponding root pulp canal annotation. Several disease types were included in this dataset such as pulpitis caries, impacted tooth and apical periodontitis to ensure the generalizability of the proposed algorithm to various clinical scenarios.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Training set: 40 labeled CBCT images, 300 unlabeled CBCT images

Validation set: 20 labeled CBCT images

Test set: 20 labeled CBCT images

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The challenge is designed for benchmarking semi-supervised learning methods. Thus, only a small set of cases of root pulp canal of CBCT are labeled and a large number of unlabeled cases can be used for training.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The data are from a large real-life scenarios, thus the class distribution is representative of the real-world distribution.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

There is no unseen teeth types in the testing set. All the testing cases will be hidden from participants and the Docker container will be used for submission.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The root pulp canal were annotated by 15 dentists. Twelve junior dentists with at least two years of experience manually marked all root pulp canal. Three senior experts with at least ten years of experience were invited to evaluate the root pulp canal annotations.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For 3D CBCT scans, professional annotation software ITKSNAP (<http://www.itksnap.org/pmwiki/pmwiki.php>) is in charge of performing the annotations for dentists.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Twelve junior dentists first annotate the root pulp canal and the teeth area. Next, the senior dentists experts assessed the annotation quality, and marked a quality level (excellent, good, fail and poor) on each tooth annotation. "Excellent" annotations were deemed satisfactory and retained without further adjustments. "Good" annotations were fine-tuning according to the experts' feedback. "Fair" and "Poor" annotations and their feedback were put back into the unlabelled data pool and were marked again. To ensure the consistency of the annotation, we perform the following operation: 1. randomly selected 30% cases were annotated by all annotators; 2. Calculated ICC coefficients; 3. Assessed multi-annotator agreement using Fleiss' Kappa; Re-annotate the cases with low ICC and Fleiss' Kappa.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No preprocessing steps are required.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

Error is unavoidable in medical image segmentation. Images were annotated by 15 dentists including twelve junior dentists and three senior dentists. Since much of the annotation process is manual, there may be inaccuracies in the root region or the pulp area. Fortunately, the quality control approach will largely reduce this source of error. Moreover, we will have a github repository to collect feedbacks from participants about possible errors that they discover in the dataset. This strategy was also used in MICCAI KiTS and FLARE Challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

None.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The segmentation inference results are evaluated using dice similarity coefficient (DSC), Normalized Surface Dice (NSD), Intersection over Union (IoU).

All metrics will be used to compute the ranking. We will release the code on how to calculate the eight performance metrics with the python3 version.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The three metrics are complementary. Specifically, Dice Similarity Coefficient is used to measure the region error. Normalized Surface Dice is used to measure the boundary error. Intersection over Union is used to measure the degree of overlap between the root canal area, the tooth area, and the ground truth.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking scheme includes the following three steps:

Step 1. Compute the four metrics for each testing case between the ground truth and the results from the participants.

Step 2. Take the mean of these metrics over the test cases, and rank separately among the teams.

Step 3. A final overall rank is given by taking the average of these ranks. In the case of equal average rankings for two teams, they are considered tied.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The main benefit of this ranking scheme is that it can aggregate the metrics with different dimensions. A similar ranking scheme was also employed in MICCAI BraTS Challenge.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

We will exclude the participants who fail to report on the whole testing set. Besides the statistical values such as mean, standard deviation of the metrics, we use the p-value in Wilcoxon test to assess whether the top performing/ranking algorithms are significantly better than the rest of algorithms. To ensure statistical reliability of rankings, we plan to implement the statistical significance testing via bootstrap resamples for the teams, to avoid the uncertainty occurred in the test phase.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The Wilcoxon test is chosen because it is non-parametric and allows us to perform the analysis with minimal hypotheses, and the Bootstrap is a simple nonparametric method that relies on minimal assumptions.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

These further analyses will be discussed in a further publication after the challenge.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A